

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0963-3499>

FACTORS AFFECTING THE DEVELOPMENT OF MINERALS IN THE KASHKADARYO REGION

Sultanov Shukhrat Adxamovich

Associate Professor,

Karshi State Technical University

E-mail: sultonovshuxrat87@gmail.com

Abstract. This article analyzes the role of natural-geographic and geological factors in the development of minerals in the mountainous regions of the Kashkadarya region. The impact of climate, relief, seismic activity and water resources on the mining processes is highlighted, and proposals are made to maintain ecological balance. Also, mining and geological conditions and the impact of mineral deposits on industrial sectors are scientifically covered.

Keywords: Kashkadarya, mountainous regions, minerals, natural-geographic factors, environmental safety, mining and geological conditions.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada Qashqadaryo viloyatining tog'li hududlaridagi tabiiy-geografik va geologik omillarning foydali qazilmalarni o'zlashtirishdagi o'rni tahlil qilingan. Iqlim, relyef, seysmik faoliyat va suv resurslarining qazib olish jarayonlariga ta'siri yoritilib, ekologik muvozanatni saqlashga doir takliflar berilgan. Shuningdek, kon-geologik sharoitlar va foydali qazilma konlarining sanoat tarmoqlariga ta'siri ham ilmiy asosda yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Qashqadaryo, tog'li hududlar, foydali qazilmalar, tabiiy-geografik omillar, ekologik xavfsizlik, kon-geologik sharoit.

Аннотация. В статье анализируется роль природно-географических и геологических факторов в освоении полезных ископаемых в горных районах Кашкадарьинской области. Освещено влияние климата, рельефа, сейсмической активности и водных ресурсов на процессы добычи полезных ископаемых, а также даны предложения по поддержанию экологического равновесия. Также научно освещены

горно-геологические условия и влияние месторождений полезных ископаемых на промышленные отрасли.

Ключевые слова: *Кашкадарья, горные районы, полезные ископаемые, природно-географические факторы, экологическая безопасность, горно-геологические условия.*

Introduction. Kashkadarya region is located in the southern part of the Republic of Uzbekistan and is a region rich in natural resources, in particular minerals. In particular, the mountainous regions of the region - the Hissar mountain range, the Zarafshan range and their foothills - are distinguished by their diverse geological structures and mining and geological conditions. In these regions, deposits of coal, marble, limestone, sandstone, iron, polymetallic ores, oil, natural gas and other minerals have been identified.

Natural and geographical conditions (climate, relief, hydrological network, flora and fauna) are among the main factors determining the possibilities of using these resources. The complex relief of mountainous regions, the presence of geologically active zones, water supply and environmental conditions play an important role in the extraction of minerals and their industrial introduction.

This article analyzes the natural and geographical factors in the use of minerals in the mountainous regions of Kashkadarya region, and gives scientific and practical recommendations for their rational use.

Discussion. Natural and geographical location of the Kashkadarya region. The Kashkadarya region is located in the southwestern part of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in the Amu Darya valley and the western foothills of the Hissar mountain range. The region borders on Samarkand in the northeast, Bukhara in the west, and the Republic of Tajikistan in the south. The total area of the region is 28.6 thousand km².

The region is geographically divided into two main parts: mountainous and lowland areas. The mountainous part occupies the western branches of the Hissar range, especially a large part of the Dehqanabad, Kamashi, Guzor, Shahrisabz, Kitab and Yakkabag districts. These mountainous zones are very rich in natural resources, in particular, minerals.

Methods. Geological structure and minerals of the region. The Kashkadarya region is located at the junction of geologically ancient platforms and orogenic zones, where geological processes were highly active. Strata from the Jurassic, Cretaceous, Paleogene, and Neogene periods are especially common in mountainous areas.

Table 1

The main minerals identified in the region are:

- coal (Kattaqum coal fields)
- oil and natural gas (Guzar, Mubarak, Chorsari and other fields)
- limestone and marble (in Kitob and Shahrissabz districts)
- polymetallic ores (iron, lead, zinc)
- tin, molybdenum and other rare metals (partly in mountainous areas).

Table 2

These resources constitute an important raw material base for industry, construction and energy sectors.

Features of the climate and relief of mountainous regions. The climate of mountainous regions is continental, rainy in spring and autumn, and hot and dry in summer. Winters are cold, sometimes there is a risk of avalanches. Such climate variability has a significant impact on excavation, transportation and infrastructure construction.

The relief is complex and varies in height from 500 to 4000 meters. In particular, the Shahrisabz and Kitab mountain ranges, the Kyzyl-Suv, Oktov and Kokbulak ranges are geologically active zones. Most of the mineral deposits are located in these regions, which requires complex engineering solutions for their development.

The influence of natural and geographical factors on the use of minerals. The use of minerals in the mountainous regions of the Kashkadarya region is directly related to natural and geographical factors. In particular:

Relief: The complex mountainous terrain creates problems for the construction of large technical equipment, vehicles and infrastructure. For example, the construction of roads and the placement of equipment in the Shargun and Boysun coal mines require significant costs.

Climate: The need to adapt to the production regime arises during the snowy winters and dry summers. In winter, access roads to the mines freeze, and in summer, the dusty environment poses a health hazard.

Figure 1. Geological map of Kashkadarya region.

Water resources: The presence of rivers and springs in mountainous areas sometimes facilitates industrial water supply near mines, but the issue of water scarcity is also relevant. This is especially important in metallurgical or mining ore washing processes.

Seismic activity: The mountainous zones of Kashkadarya are among the seismically active regions, which requires increased safety measures when deep mining of mineral deposits.

Problems of ecological safety and preservation of natural balance. The use of minerals affects the natural and geographical balance. Ecological problems in mountainous areas are as follows:

Erosion and landslides: Blasting operations in mountainous terrain lead to instability of the soil layer.

Reduction of biodiversity: As a result of mining operations, unique flora and fauna are at risk of extinction (for example, around the Kitab State Biosphere Reserve).

Table 3

Air and water pollution: During the extraction of coal, gas and metal ores, gases such as dust, SO₂, NO₂ are released. Pollution of water bodies near the mine poses a health risk to the local population.

Conclusions and recommendations.

The process of using minerals in the mountainous regions of the Kashkadarya region is associated with complex natural and geographical conditions. These factors directly affect the extraction, transportation, processing and environmental safety measures.

It is recommended:

- Design mining facilities taking into account the relief of the territories.
- Introduce an environmental monitoring system in mountainous areas.
- Prefer underground mines over open pit mining (they cause less environmental damage).
- Protect local water sources and install filtration systems.

References.

1. Faizullaev M.A., Nurmatov A.U., Khujakulov S.U. Economic geographical characteristics of the development of industrial networks of Kashadarya region // Proceedings of International Conference on Modern Science and Scientific Studies Hosted online from Paris, France. P. 125-134.
2. Файзуллаев.М.А., Жанубий Ўзбекистонда аграр-индустриал циклининг шаклланиши ва ривожланиши. Ўзбекистон География жамияти ахбороти. 2015, 46, 103-105.
3. Karimov, M. (2018). O‘zbekiston geologiyasi asoslari. Toshkent: Fan nashriyoti.
4. Rasulov, A. (2020). “Qashqadaryo viloyatining tabiiy resurslari va ulardan foydalanish istiqbollari”, Geografiya va tabiiy resurslar, 4(2), 44–51.
5. State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Geology and Mineral Resources. (2023). Regional geological reports.
6. Султонов Ш.А., Навотова Д. И., Алиева Д. И. Қашқадарё вилояти минерал ресурслари ва улардан фойдаланишнинг географик хусусиятлари //Science and education in the modern world: challenges of the XXI century" Nur-Sultan, Kazakhstan. – 2020. – С. 12-15.
7. Sultonov Shuxrat Adxamovich, Navotova Dilnoza Ibrogimovna, O‘zbekistonda rangli metallarning geografik tarqalishi va foydalanish xususiyatlari. Экономика и социум. - №2(117)-1 2024, 682-690 betlar, 2024-yil. <http://www.iupr.ru> , ISSN 2225-1545
8. Sh.A.Sultonov, D.N.Mavlonova, Z.B.Boyoqulova, Foydali qazilmalarning sanoat turlarini o‘rganishga doir ma’lumotlarni qisqacha tahlil qilish. Экономика и социум №1(128)-2 2025, 454-459 betlar, 2025-yil, www.iupr.ru, ISSN 2225-1545.

9. Sh.A.Sultonov, Qashqadaryo viloyati tog‘li hududlarida foydali qazilmalarni geografik tarqalishi. Экономика и социум №3(130)-1 2025, www.iupr.ru. ЭС-2025-030076, ISSN 2225-1545.

10. Zohidov, S. (2017). O‘zbekistonning tog‘li hududlarida ekologik muammolar. Toshkent: Ekosan.

11. UNDP Uzbekistan. (2021). Sustainable use of natural resources in mountainous regions of Central Asia.

